

REBUILD

Working Paper

**REPowerEU:
Next Generation EU's
architecture beyond the
pandemic**

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REPowerEU: Next Generation EU's architecture beyond the pandemic

Rosalba Famà*

Abstract: Russian unlawful invasion of Ukraine had direct and indirect consequences on the EU energy independence and the implementation of the Recovery Plan (NGEU). To tackle the effects of the energy crisis and its potential impact on the EU economic recovery, the Commission proposed a REPowerEU plan that amends NGEU to make it fit with the current urgencies. This paper presents a legal analysis of REPowerEU, which is the first example of NGEU's architecture beyond the pandemic. This analysis shows that although conceived as a one-off tool, its legal structure can be replicated. Moreover, this paper reflects on three preliminary findings. First, the adoption of REPowerEU continues the path toward the transfer of fiscal powers to the EU. Second, REPowerEU resources to be distributed in the form of non-repayable support will be placed outside the European budget. Third, to re-channel EU funds to the current needs, REPowerEU introduces an element of flexibility in the use of cohesion funds.

Keywords: REPowerEU, Next Generation EU, Recovery plans, energy crisis, Covid-19, emergency, green transition, fossil fuels.

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1. Introduction

The EU decided to adopt a plan designed to break free from dependency on Russian fossil fuels, named REPowerEU.¹ The latter is a new energy program that is embedded in the legal framework of Next Generation EU (NGEU). After the outbreak of the pandemic, the European Union adopted a recovery plan to prepare for the next generation of European citizens. It consists of an innovative financial assistance mechanism that links the disbursement of European funds to Member States with the enforcement of a reform and investment agenda.² Since NGEU's inception, the temporal and exceptional nature of the Recovery plan has been discussed by many.³ This paper describes the legal architecture of REPowerEU, which is the first example of NGEU beyond the pandemic. This analysis shows that although conceived as a one-off tool, NGEU's legal structure can be replicated and adapted to tackle further emergencies which go beyond the pandemic.

On 24 February 2022, Russia unlawfully invaded the territory of Ukraine. The Russian military aggression against Ukraine has disrupted the global energy system⁴ and heightened the EU energy security concerns.⁵ This is so because the EU was highly dependent on gas, oil, and coal imports from Russia.⁶ Hardship caused in the energy sector resulted in high energy prices and supply shortages. These circumstances represent a threat for the Union's strategic autonomy and economic recovery, including the enforcement of the EU recovery plan. To deal with these challenges, the Commission

Please note that all documents have been last accessed on 16.2.2023.

¹ Commission, Press Release 'Commission welcomes political agreement on REPowerEU under the Recovery and Resilience Facility' 14 December 2022, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_7717>.

² Commission, "Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814", 2022/0164 (COD), See the Explanatory memorandum, 1, Brussels 18.05.2022.

³ See Martin Nettesheim, 'Legally Feasible, Constitutionally Dubious: Establishing, Next Generation Europe on the Basis of EU Secondary Legislation', *VerfBlog*, 12 April 2020, <<https://verfassungsblog.de/legally-feasible-constitutionally-dubious/>>. Bruno de Witte 'The European Union's Covid-19 Recovery Plan: the legal engineering of an economic policy shift', *Common Market Law Review* 2021, 58. Päivi Leino-Sandberg and Matthis Ruffert 'Next Generation EU and its constitutional ramifications: A critical assessment', *Common Market Law Review* 59. Federico Fabbrini 'The Legal Architecture of the Economic Responses to COVID-19: EMU beyond the Pandemic', 2022, 60, *Journal of Common Market Studies* 186; Lucas Guttenberg and others, 'Everything will be different: How pandemic is changing EU economic governance' (2021) Jacques Delors Centre, Policy Brief, 11 February 2021, 2. Federico Fubini, "'If it works, Next Generation EU will change the face of the Union": an interview with European Commissioner for the Economy Paolo Gentiloni', in Simone Disegni (ed.), *Europe at a crossroads after the shock* (Milan, 2020), 25 in which Gentiloni states that if NGEU is successfully implemented it could become a permanent rather than a temporary feature of the EU.

⁴ International Energy Agency, 'Global Energy Crisis. How the energy crisis started, how global energy markets are impacting our daily life and what governments are doing about it'. Available at <<https://www.iea.org/topics/global-energy-crisis>> Commission, COM(2022) 230 final, "Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan", Brussels 18.05.2022.

⁵ European Parliament, 'New EU regulation on gas storage' Briefing, EU legislation in progress. Available at <[https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/729393/EPRS_BRI\(2022\)729393_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/BRIE/2022/729393/EPRS_BRI(2022)729393_EN.pdf)>.

⁶ Rebecca Leber, 'Europe can lead the way through an energy crisis without more fossil fuels', 26 March 2022, *Vox* available at <<https://www.vox.com/22983893/europe-us-lng-gas-russia-climate>>.

proposed a REPowerEU strategy⁷ that, as the name suggests, has the final aim of re-powering the EU's energy autonomy by securing our energy supply. REPowerEU encompasses a comprehensive plan with a broad range of initiatives such as a new Regulation on gas storage,⁸ a proposal on energy market design,⁹ a proposal on a Platform for joint gas purchase,¹⁰ and an EU solar¹¹ and renewable strategy.¹² Within the REPowerEU strategy, the Commission proposed to reform the NGEU to secure “a successful and sustainable recovery from the Covid-19 crisis.”¹³ In particular, REPowerEU amends the Regulation establishing a Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF), the largest NGEU's spending programme in terms of the budget assigned to it. Both the comprehensive plan initiatives and subsequent amendments to NGEU legal acts are grasped under ‘REPowerEU Plan’ in the remainder of this paper.

This paper proceeds as follows. Section I sets the background of the REPowerEU proposal by describing the geopolitical context and rationale of its adoption. Section II analyses the legal architecture of REPowerEU. Section III looks at REPowerEU governance and highlights how the Recovery and Resilience Plans provide a European framework to deliver on strategic objectives. Section IV studies the legal innovations driven by REPowerEU. The last section concludes the argument developed in this paper.

⁷ Commission, Press Release ‘REPowerEU: joint European action for more affordable, secure and sustainable energy’ 8 March 2022, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_1511> and ‘REPowerEU: A plan to rapidly reduce dependence on Russian fossil fuels and fast forward the green transition’, 18 May 2022. Available at <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_22_3131>.

⁸ Commission “Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2017/1938 of the European Parliament and of the Council concerning measures to safeguard the security of gas supply and Regulation (EC) n°715/2009 of the European Parliament and of the Council on conditions for access to natural gas transmission networks.” This Regulation was adopted in June 2022 and required Member States to fill in at least 80% of their storage capacity by 1 November 2022.

⁹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European economic and social Committee and the Committee of the regions Short-Term Energy Market Interventions and Long-Term Improvements to the Electricity Market Design – a course for action. COM/2022/236 final.

¹⁰ Proposal for a Council Regulation Enhancing solidarity through better coordination of gas purchases, exchanges of gas across borders and reliable price benchmarks. COM/2022/549 final.

¹¹ Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European economic and social Committee and the Committee of the Regions EU solar energy strategy. COM(2022) 221 final.

¹² Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan. COM(2022) 230 final Brussels 18.05.2022.

¹³ Commission, “Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814”. 2022/0164 (COD), See the Explanatory memorandum, 1, Brussels 18.05.2022.

2. The geo-energetic context and the steps toward the adoption of a REPowerEU strategy

The unprovoked Russian military aggression of Ukraine disrupted the world's energy system, with Russia being among the largest fossil fuel exporters worldwide.¹⁴ Therefore, the immediate consequence of the unlawful invasion was the deepest energy crisis ever experienced in modern history that had caused widespread hardship as a result of high energy prices.¹⁵

These circumstances drastically impacted the Union's economy and radically changed the geo-energetic context in which the EU must position itself.¹⁶ Indeed, the EU imports up to 90% of its gas consumption, and Russia previously contributed more than 40% of the demand. Russia also provided 27% of oil and 46% of coal imports to the EU.¹⁷ The interdependence between western and eastern Europe was strengthened by crucial physical infrastructures, such as the gas pipeline Brotherhood which transits through Ukraine, Yamal through Poland, and the Nord Stream which crosses the Baltic Sea and the territory of Germany (see Annex 1). Since the Second World War, both households and industry in the EU benefited from the massive flow of gas from Russia at low prices.¹⁸

Currently, coal and crude oil imports from Russia are covered by sanctions.¹⁹ Moreover, in recent months, the EU's gas supply from Russia has been repeatedly interrupted²⁰ and the Nord Stream II pipeline was sabotaged.²¹ As it is self-evident, the EU can no longer rely on Russia as a trustable

¹⁴ International Energy Agency, 'Energy fact sheet: why does Russian oil and gas matter?' 21 March 2022. Available at <<https://www.iea.org/articles/energy-fact-sheet-why-does-russian-oil-and-gas-matter/>>.

¹⁵ Commission, "Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814", 2022/0164 (COD), 1.

¹⁶ Massimo Amato and others, 'Towards a Mediterranean Community for Renewables. Building a new community process with the southern shore of the Mediterranean: Energy transition and geopolitics in the age of war ecology'. Groupe d'études géopolitiques, 28 November 2022 available at <<https://geopolitique.eu/en/2022/11/28/towards-a-mediterranean-community-for-renewables/>>.

¹⁷ Commission, "Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814", 2022/0164 (COD), 1.

¹⁸ See International Energy Agency, 'Gas Market and Russian Supply', 2022 available at <<https://www.iea.org/reports/russian-supplies-to-global-energy-markets/gas-market-and-russian-supply-2>>.

¹⁹ See Council Regulation (EU) 2022/576 of 8 April 2022 amending Regulation (EU) No 833/2014 concerning restrictive measures in view of Russia's actions destabilizing the situation in Ukraine. See Council Decision (CFSP) 2022/1909 of 6 October 2022 amending Decision 2014/512/CFSP concerning restrictive measures in view of Russia's actions destabilizing the situation in Ukraine.

²⁰ Kate Connolly, 'Nord Stream 1: Russia switches off gas pipelines citing maintenance', 31 August 2022, The Guardian.

²¹ Rebecca Ruiz and Justin Scheck, 'In Nord Stream mystery, Baltic Seabed provides a nearly ideal crime scene', 26 December 2022, The New York Times.

energy supplier²² and the adoption of an enfranchisement strategy is more than ever indispensable for the survival of the EU.²³

Immediately after the Russian aggression, the Heads of State and Government of the EU met informally in Versailles on 10-11 March 2022. They addressed three crucial issues for the EU, namely bolstering defence capabilities, reducing energy dependency, and building a more robust economy.²⁴ On this occasion, EU leaders adopted the “Versailles declaration” where they agreed on the need to phase out dependency on Russian gas, oil, and coal imports and tasked the Commission to present a proposal for this purpose.²⁵ European leaders reiterated the invitation to the Commission to submit an ambitious energy plan at the European Council on 24-25 March 2022, which also focused on high energy prices and their negative impact on citizens and businesses.²⁶

Finally, on 18 May 2022, the Commission issued a comprehensive strategy to re-power the EU.²⁷ Among the measures envisaged, the Commission proposes to modify Regulation (EU) 2021/241 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility, which is the cornerstone of Next Generation EU.²⁸ For this purpose, the Commission invites Member States to insert an addendum to their Recovery Plans with new reforms and investments aimed at diversifying the energy supply and reducing dependency on fossil fuels.²⁹ Therefore, the facility is tasked with new actions contributing towards the security of energy supplies to the EU.

3. The legal architecture of REPowerEU

3.1 The legal structure of Next Generation EU: a sui-generis trilateral construction

The new European energy plan will be embedded in the legal architecture of Next Generation EU, therefore, to have a full understanding of REPowerEU’s legal structure and functioning it is essential

²² Commission, “Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan”, COM(2022) 230 final Brussels 18.05.2022.

²³ Massimo Amato and others, cit. note 16.

²⁴ Informal meeting of the Heads of State or Government, Versailles Declaration, 10 and 11 March 2022, 3. Available at <<https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/54773/20220311-versailles-declaration-en.pdf>> .

²⁵ Ibid, 5 and 6. The targets to be achieved were identified as follows: a) accelerating the overall reliance of the EU on fossil fuels; b) diversifying energy supplies; c) developing a hydrogen market for Europe; d) speeding up the development of renewables; e) completing and improving the interconnection of European gas and electricity networks and fully synchronising our power grids throughout the EU; f) reinforcing EU contingency planning for security of supply; g) improving energy efficiency and the management of energy consumption, and promoting a more circular approach to manufacturing and consumption patterns.

²⁶ European Council Meeting 24 and 25 March 2022, Conclusions. Available at <<https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-1-2022-INIT/en/pdf>>.

²⁷ Commission, “Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan”, COM(2022) 230 final, Brussels 18.05.2022.

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Ibid.

to grasp the main elements which characterize NGEU. This is useful in identifying the extent of the amendments brought by REPowerEU to NGEU and discussing how REPowerEU updates NGEU to make it fit with the emerging priorities. This analysis is also indispensable to support the thesis that REPowerEU is the first example of NGEU's architecture beyond the pandemic. As we will see, NGEU is proving to be flexible enough to include new targets and may be used as a blueprint for further actions to address future crises.

The NGEU is an unprecedented package that allows the Commission to borrow massive sums of money on the financial markets on behalf of the EU,³⁰ up to 750 billion euro to finance reforms and investments necessary to tackle the consequences of the pandemic. It represents a temporary fiscal space, which is capable to finance EU spending programmes to promote European public goods.³¹ However, the political agreement reached at the European Council meeting held on 17-21 July 2020 foresaw that the borrowing power granted to the Commission must stay limited in size, duration and scope.³² The temporality and exceptionality character of the EU's Covid-19 recovery plan was transposed into the text of the Regulation establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility,³³ the Regulation establishing a Recovery Instrument and the Decision on the own resources.

NGEU's legal structure is characterized by three components which are based on a "multifaceted legal constellation".³⁴ Firstly, a revised Own Resources Decision,³⁵ secondly, the Regulation establishing the Recovery Instrument³⁶ and thirdly, the Regulation establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF or Facility).³⁷ REPowerEU builds on this trilateral legal construction while amending only the Regulation establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

3.2 The Decision on the system of own resources of the European Union

The first component of NGEU is the Council Decision on the system of Own Resources based on Article 311 TFEU. This act establishes the resources through which the Union finances itself. Due to its strategic importance, it requires the Council to vote unanimously, and it needs to be ratified by

³⁰ See Richard Crowe, "The EU recovery plan: New dynamics in the financing of the EU budget" in Barrett et al. (Eds.), *The Future of Legal Europe: Will We Trust in It? Liber Amicorum in Honour of Wolfgang Heusel* (Springer, 2021)

³¹ Federico Fabbrini, cit. note 3, 193.

³² Special meeting of the European Council 17-21 July 2020, Conclusions. Available at <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/45109/210720-euco-final-conclusions-en.pdf>.

³³ See Recital 6 of the Regulation establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

³⁴ *Ibid*, 191.

³⁵ Council Decision (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053 on the system of own resources of the European Union and repealing Decision 2014/335/EU Euratom.

³⁶ Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2094 of 14 December 2020 establishing a European Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the Covid-19 crisis.

³⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/241 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 February 2021 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility.

each Member State consistently with their national constitutional requirements.³⁸ This Decision is regarded as having a semi-constitutional legal value,³⁹ although it is formally an act of secondary legislation. This special legal value can be explained in two ways, first by looking at the legislative procedure for its adoption, which involves the ratification by the Member States before its entering into force; second, considering that the EU annual budget must comply with this Decision.

The revised Own Resources Decision plays two crucial roles within the legal construction of NGEU. On the one hand, it authorizes the Commission to borrow funds from the financial markets on behalf of the EU. On the other hand, the Own Resources Decision provides guarantees for the repayment of the common debt. Specifically, it increases potential GNI-based national contributions that Member States may be required to provide to cover liabilities deriving from the issuance of the common debt.⁴⁰ Both the empowerment of the EU to borrow⁴¹ and the increase of potential Member States' contributions to the European budget are temporary and confined to the need of addressing the consequences of the Covid-19 crisis.⁴² Playing these crucial roles, the Own Resources Decision is “more high profile” this time around.⁴³ REPowerEU will not involve the issuance of additional common debt,⁴⁴ rather it mobilizes the resources already borrowed in compliance with the Own Resources Decision towards new energy-related targets.

3.3 The Regulation establishing the Recovery Instrument

The second component of NGEU is the Regulation establishing the Recovery Instrument (EURI). EURI has the form of a Council Regulation and is based on Article 122 TFEU. This provision belongs to EU executive law,⁴⁵ which exceptionally justifies the exclusion of the European Parliament from the legislative procedure.⁴⁶ According to Art. 122 (1) TFEU on a proposal from the Commission and in a spirit of solidarity between the Member States, the Council can adopt measures appropriate to

³⁸ Richard Crowe, ‘An EU budget of States and citizens’, *European Law Journal* 2020, 26, 331-344, 339.

³⁹ Bruno de Witte, *cit. note 3*, 660.

⁴⁰ See on the revenue side of the European budget Cristina Fasone and Nicola Lupo, ‘The Union budget and the budgetary procedure’ in “*Oxford Principles of European Union Law. Volume I*. Edited by Professor Robert Schutze and Professor Takis Tridimas, Oxford University Press, 2018, 817.

⁴¹ See Article 5 of the Council Decision 2020/2053.

⁴² See Article 6 of the Council Decision 2020/2053.

⁴³ Richard Crowe, *cit. note 38*, 339.

⁴⁴ See also Simone Tagliapietra and others, ‘Does the European Union need an energy crisis fund?’, *Bruegel*, 11 October 2022.

⁴⁵ Karl Croonenborghs, “The European Instrument for Temporary Support to mitigate unemployment risks in an emergency (SURE) – an innovative EU financial assistance under the Treaty”, in ‘EU Law in times of pandemic. The EU Legal response to Covid-19’, edited by Dolores Utrilla and Anjum Shabbir, EU Law Press.

⁴⁶ Jean-Victor Louis, ‘Guest editorial: the no-bailout clause and rescue packages’, 47 *Common Market Law Review* 2010, 971-986. 983. Following the introduction of EURI, the Council and the European Parliament adopted a “Joint declaration of the European Parliament, the Council and the Commission on budgetary scrutiny of new proposals based on Article 122 TFEU with potential appreciable implications for the Union budget 2020/C 444 I/05”.

the economic situation. Specifically, when severe difficulties arise in the supply chain of specific products, especially in the energy sector. While Article 122 (2) TFEU states that if a Member State is severely menaced by or is facing severe difficulties due to natural disasters or exceptional situations beyond its control, the Council, on a proposal from the Commission, is allowed to grant, under certain conditions, Union financial assistance to the Member State concerned. It is worth noting that EURI does not provide directly Union financial assistance to the States, rather it lays down general arrangements for the use of the proceeds of the Union's borrowing.⁴⁷ Notwithstanding it is based on both paragraphs of Article 122 TFEU, as the first paragraph refers to a spirit of solidarity, while the second paragraph mentions natural disasters which were two key factors in facing the Covid-19 emergency.⁴⁸

The Recovery Instrument plays three different functions. Firstly, it receives the proceeds from borrowing on the financial markets,⁴⁹ so it acts as a "container".⁵⁰ Secondly, it distributes the amounts to the different spending programmes,⁵¹ the largest part of which is allocated to the Recovery and Resilience Facility.⁵² Thirdly, EURI sets the rules on the budgetary implementation of the proceeds from borrowing, in compliance with the Financial Regulation.⁵³ As it is well known, the EU is governed by the principle of budgetary balance which implies that revenues and expenditures must be in balance, as provided in Article 310 (1) TFEU. This principle has been interpreted as meaning that the EU cannot finance its expenditure by issuing debt.⁵⁴ By way of an exception, relying on the extraordinary circumstances of the pandemic, the EU is currently issuing debt to finance its expenditure which consists of non-repayable support to Member States.⁵⁵ To avoid any conflict with the principle of budgetary equilibrium, proceeds from borrowing to be used for non-repayable support under NGEU (i.e. to finance expenditure) are classified as "External assigned revenue".⁵⁶ These revenues are not subject to the normal budgetary procedure,⁵⁷ which foresees the annual scrutiny of the Council and European Parliament in their role of budgetary authority. This way of proceeding deviates from standard practices and creates a European hidden budget. As it will be analysed in detail

⁴⁷ Council of the European Union, 'Opinion of the Legal Service', 9062/20, 24 June 2020, 46-50, see par. 122.

⁴⁸ Ibid, par. 119.

⁴⁹ See Article 2 (1) of Regulation (EU) 2020/2094.

⁵⁰ Bruno de Witte, cit. note 3.

⁵¹ See Article 2 (2) of Regulation (EU) 2020/2094.

⁵² A total of 672 500 million euro is allocated to the Recovery and Resilience Facility out of 750 000 million euro.

⁵³ Regulation (EU) 2018/1046.

⁵⁴ Iann Begg, 'Breaking the shackles of austerity? Using the EU budget to achieve macroeconomic stabilization', Friedrich Ebert Stiftung, November 2012 available at <<https://library.fes.de/pdf-files/id/09450.pdf>>.

⁵⁵ Martin Nettesheim, cit. note 3.

⁵⁶ See Article 3 (1) of Regulation 2020/2094. See Bruno De Witte, cit. note 35, 663.

⁵⁷ Charles Blankart, 'The European Union's debt question: a conceptual viewpoint', Constitutional Political Economy, (4) 257-266. 259.

later, this legal “trick” has been replicated under REPowerEU without being accompanied by a reformed EU constitutional setting.

3.4 The Recovery and Resilience Facility

The third component of NGEU is the Regulation establishing Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF or Facility). As mentioned, the latter is amended by REPowerEU. The Facility is the cornerstone of both NGEU and REPowerEU. The RRF is based on Article 175 (3) TFEU, a cohesion policy legal basis. The Recovery Instrument allocates up to 672 500 million euro to the Facility. Of this amount, up to 360 billion euro will be distributed to the Member States in the form of grants, while the remaining amount of money will be made available in the form of loans to the Member States. So far, as the Commission has recognized, 225 billion euro are still available under the Facility in the form of loans because some Member States have not requested the funds.⁵⁸ REPowerEU aims at mobilizing these resources to address emerging energy issues.

The Facility is an innovative tool in the field of European fiscal governance and cohesion policy. It combines reforms to be implemented by the Member States and investments financed by European resources. Both investments and reforms are illustrated in the National Recovery and Resilience Plans (or Recovery Plans) which are drafted by the Member States. Recovery Plans take in due account the Country Specific Recommendations and identify targets and milestones to be achieved within a certain time limit, which must be no later than 31 August 2026.⁵⁹ Recovery Plans must also contribute to the green and digital transition. For these purposes, at least 57% of the allocated resources shall be destined for climate and digital targets,⁶⁰ also referred to as the “twin transition”.⁶¹

The Commission assesses whether those plans are relevant, effective, efficient and coherent.⁶² Finally, on a proposal from the Commission, the Council approves the recovery plans by means of implementing decisions.⁶³ By presenting and receiving the approval of their Recovery Plans, Member States bind themselves to multi-annual reform and investment agendas. The plans are aimed not only at mitigating the social and economic consequences of the pandemic, but also to prepare for future crises, and driving policy goals, such as the twin transition. Upon the satisfactory achievement of

⁵⁸ Commission, COM(2022) 230 final, “Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan”, Brussels 18.05.2022, 18.

⁵⁹ See Article 20 of Regulation (EU) 241/2021.

⁶⁰ See Article 16 of Regulation (EU) 241/2021.

⁶¹ Stefan Muench and others, ‘Towards a green and digital future’, EUR 31075 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2022.

⁶² See Article 19 of Regulation (EU) 241/2021.

⁶³ See Article 20 of Regulation (EU) 241/2021.

targets and milestones set in the Recovery Plans, the financial contribution is paid to the Member State concerned.⁶⁴

The Facility breaks with past mutual assistance instruments which foresaw public spending cuts in times of crisis. Spending review in times of economic distress is replaced with ambitious public investment plans, as reforms are more likely to be performed in a thriving economy.⁶⁵ This new expansionary approach marks a breaking point with the austerity paradigm which was followed up at that time.⁶⁶ Moreover, the Facility not only provides for reactive measures but rather supports preventive actions to avoid the resurfacing of crises. REPowerEU is placed within this cutting-edge context and builds on the same idea of making funds conditional to the achievements of strategic objectives agreed upon by Member States and the EU.

3.5 The Proposal for a REPowerEU plan

The REPowerEU proposal⁶⁷ is fully embedded in the Next Generation EU legal framework. This is particularly evident by looking at two aspects. First, the proposal amends the Recovery and Resilience Facility adding a new chapter dedicated to the energy crisis and inviting Member States to update their Recovery Plans accordingly.⁶⁸ Second, NGEU unused loans will be re-directed towards the new energy-related targets. Indeed, the Facility will be the linchpin of the new REPowerEU plan.⁶⁹

Moving to the legal structure of REPowerEU, as anticipated, the plan will have the form of a Regulation of the Council and the European Parliament which amends Regulation (EU) 2021/241 establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) based on Article 175 (3) TFEU.

REPowerEU also amends Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 which lays down Common provisions on European funds⁷⁰ and Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 which regulates the European Agricultural

⁶⁴ See Article 24(6) first paragraph of Regulation 241/2021.

⁶⁵ Fabio Panetta, 'After the crisis: Economic lessons from the pandemic', Politico, 27 July 2021.

⁶⁶ Maja Lukic Radovic and Marija Vlajkovic, 'How Firm Are the Bonds That Tie the EU Together? EU Rule of Law Conditionality Mechanism and the next Generation EU Recovery Fund' 5 ECLIC, 79, 2021. See also Iann Begg, cit. note 54.

⁶⁷ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

⁶⁸ See The explanatory memorandum of the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814, 7.

⁶⁹ Ibid, 4.

⁷⁰ Regulation (EU) 2021/1060 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 June 2021 laying down common provisions on the European Regional Development Fund, the European Social Fund Plus, the Cohesion Fund, the Just Transition Fund and the European Maritime, Fisheries and Aquaculture Fund and financial rules for those and for the Asylum, Migration and Integration Fund, the Internal Security Fund and the Instrument for Financial Support for Border Management and Visa Policy.

Guarantee Fund (EAGF) as well as the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD),⁷¹ based on Article 177 TFEU. Targeted amendments of the aforementioned Union's legal acts aim at pooling economic resources to a new "basket" of the RRF, which will be dedicated to financing energy-related investments and reforms. The proposed Regulation affects the organization of the Structural funds, by increasing the possibility to transfer cohesion policy funds to the RRF.⁷²

Finally, REPowerEU amends Directive 2003/87/EC⁷³ establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community and Decision (EU) 2015/184 on the Market Stability Reserve for the Union greenhouse gas.⁷⁴ These proposed amendments are based on Article 192 (1) TFEU and Article 194 (2) TFEU and aim at introducing revisions to the system for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Union to secure energy supply.⁷⁵

The following sections analyze the legal basis of REPowerEU and the two pillars of the proposal which are new REPowerEU objectives and new resources financing those objectives.

3.6 The legal basis for amending the RRF

As it was anticipated, the RRF Regulation and its REPowerEU amendments are based on Article 175 (3) TFEU. This provision is placed within the TFEU's Title headed 'Economic, social and territorial cohesion' and provides that if measures are needed outside the scope of pre-existing Structural Funds, then such actions can be adopted under the ordinary legislative procedure and after having consulted the Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions. Therefore, this article allows the introduction of new funds and actions, different from pre-existing Structural funds, as in the case of the Recovery and Resilience Facility. It is worth noting that this provision is drafted in very broad terms and there is not a clear delimitation of cohesion policies within the Treaties. Therefore, as noted by De Witte, Article 175 (3) TFEU contains a 'flexibility clause'.⁷⁶ In the past, this clause was used

⁷¹ Regulation (EU) 2021/2115 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 2 December 2021 establishing rules on support for strategic plans to be drawn up by Member States under the common agricultural policy (CAP Strategic Plans) and financed by the European Agricultural Guarantee Fund (EAGF) and by the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD) and repealing Regulations (EU) No 1305/2013 and (EU) No 1307/2013.

⁷² Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814, 3.

⁷³ Directive 2003/87/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 October 2003 establishing a scheme for greenhouse gas emission allowance trading within the Community and amending Council Directive 96/61/EC.

⁷⁴ Decision (EU) 2015/1814 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 6 October 2015 concerning the establishment and operation of a market stability reserve for the Union greenhouse gas emission trading scheme and amending Directive 2003/87/EC.

⁷⁵ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814,3.

⁷⁶ Bruno de Witte, cit. note 3, 655.

to deliver on EU policy goals in the absence of a clear legal basis elsewhere in the Treaties⁷⁷ and it was creatively relied upon to set up an unprecedented Recovery and Resilience Facility.⁷⁸

According to the Commission, REPowerEU aims at enhancing cohesion by supporting actions to increase energy security of the EU.⁷⁹ The current geopolitical context has shown significant disparities between regions of the EU in terms of dependency on fossil fuels, especially those imported from Russia.⁸⁰ REPowerEU will distribute resources favouring Member States most negatively affected by the energy crisis considering regional differences. To this purpose, the distribution criteria will consider Member States energy dependency rate and the share of fossil fuels in gross inland energy consumption.⁸¹ Therefore, Article 175 (3) TFEU was considered by the Commission an appropriate legal basis for REPowerEU, as the plan aims at boosting cohesion among European regions that have been differently affected by the energy crisis.

3.7 The REPowerEU objectives

The first pillar of REPowerEU is the introduction of a new objective to the Recovery and Resilience Facility, consisting of increasing the resilience of the Union energy system.⁸² This general target will be reached addressing two sub-targets: decreasing dependence on fossil fuels and diversifying energy supplies at Union level.⁸³ In such a way, the Facility not only addresses the social and economic consequences of Covid-19 crisis but also the energetic consequences of the war in Ukraine, defined as “REPowerEU objectives”.⁸⁴

As observed by the Council Legal Service, the final objectives of Recovery Instrument are pursued via the implementation of autonomous spending programs, including the RRF.⁸⁵ This means that the Recovery Instrument and the RRF are inherently interlinked. Therefore, the RRF must translate in its

⁷⁷ Ibid.

⁷⁸ On the concept of “constitutional creativity” see Eleanor Spaventa, ‘Constitutional creativity or constitutional deception? Acts of the Member States acting collectively and jurisdiction of the Court of Justice’ *Common Market Law Review* 2021, 58, 1697-1730.

⁷⁹ See the Explanatory Memorandum to the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814, 4.

⁸⁰ Ibid.

⁸¹ European Parliament, Press Release “REPowerEU: deal on energy measures in national recovery and resilience plans”, 14 December 2022 available at <<https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20221212IPR64514/repowereu-deal-on-energy-measures-in-national-recovery-plans>>.

⁸² See Article 1 of the Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

⁸³ Ibid.

⁸⁴ Being the Facility financed by the Recovery Instrument it needs to respect the conditions applicable to it, which are exceptionality, temporality and economic in nature. The Facility as amended by REPowerEU still complies with these conditions.

⁸⁵ Council of the European Union, ‘Opinion of the Legal Service’, 9062/20, 24 June 2020, 50, par. 122.

content the requirements that apply to the Recovery Instrument, which are exceptionality, temporality and economic nature of the measures envisaged.⁸⁶ The RRF, as amended by REPowerEU, still complies with these conditions. Indeed, new REPowerEU measures address the energy crisis, are limited in time and are of an economic nature. Moreover, the Union's energy security is indispensable to secure a successful recovery from the pandemic. Indeed, growing energy prices may slow down the economic rebound. Therefore, the successful enforcement of the energy objectives will contribute to the achievement of milestones and targets in the current National Recovery Plans.

New measures that Member States are invited to adopt must contribute to the REPowerEU objectives. They must consist of improving energy infrastructures and facilities to meet immediate security of supply needs, addressing internal and cross-border energy transmission bottlenecks, interventions in buildings and critical energy infrastructure, increasing the production of clean energy by speeding-up renewables and boosting the production of related technologies. To accompany those changes, the workforce must also be requalified towards green skills.⁸⁷ Actions needed to foster independence and security of Union's energy supply are not completely misaligned with the Union's 2030 and 2050 climate targets.⁸⁸ REPowerEU accelerates the process in reaching those targets and building synergies with ongoing projects. Indeed, the REPowerEU proposal is consistent with the spirit of other Union's initiatives to enhance the Union's energy resilience, such as the Commission's "Fit for 55" proposal.⁸⁹

3.8 REPowerEU financing: between flexibility and new revenue

The second pillar of REPowerEU is its financing structure. Phasing out the dependency on Russian fossil fuels requires huge investments to improve the European energy infrastructure and to lead the green transition. To this purpose, REPowerEU aims at pooling resources for new energy-related targets and milestones. The financial envelope of REPowerEU will be funded by three different sources of finance.⁹⁰ First, by revenues from the auctioning of the Emission Trading System (ETS) allowances.⁹¹ Second, by mobilizing NGEU loans that, so far, have not been requested by the Member

⁸⁶ Ibid, 58-60.

⁸⁷ See Article 21 c, Commission Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

⁸⁸ See point (11) of Article 2 of Regulation (EU) 2018/19.

⁸⁹ European Commission, Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions 'Fit for 55': delivering the EU's 2030 Climate Target on the way to climate neutrality COM/2021/550 final.

⁹⁰ Rosalba Famà, 'REPowerEU: a European fiscal space beyond the pandemic', EU Law Analysis, 4 January 2023 available at <<http://eulawanalysis.blogspot.com>>.

⁹¹ See Article 1, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

States.⁹² Third, Member States will be granted greater flexibility to transfer resources allocated to them under shared management programmes to the Facility.⁹³

As to the first typology of funding, revenues coming from the ETS will be made available to the Member States in the form of non-repayable support.⁹⁴ This means that Member States will be able to request additional support under the Facility in the form of grants, up to 20 billion euro. To this purpose, REPowerEU amends Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814,⁹⁵ authorizing the auctioning of the allowances released from the Market Stability Reserve until the total amount of revenue obtained from such auctioning has reached 20 billion euro. The auctioning of ETS allowances destined for the Recovery and Resilience Facility is only temporary and limited in size. Indeed, it is authorized for the period until 31 December 2026 and until the amount has reached 20 billion euro.⁹⁶ Revenues obtained from this auctioning, instead of being assigned to the Market Stability Reserve, are exceptionally made available to the Recovery and Resilience Facility and used to support exclusively reforms and investments included in the REPowerEU chapters.⁹⁷ Similarly to NGEU, these amounts to be used for non-repayable support will be classified as external assigned revenue for the purposes of Article 21 of the Financial Regulation.⁹⁸ The budgetary profiles will be discussed in Section IV.

The second way of financing the REPowerEU chapter consists in mobilizing unspent loans under NGEU. As anticipated, the Commission assessed that, to date, 225 billion euro is still available within the Facility.⁹⁹ That is because some Member States requested only grants in their National Recovery and Resilience Plans. In fact, some Member States, like Germany¹⁰⁰ and Finland¹⁰¹ have no appetite in NGEU's loans because they come with ambitious reform agendas attached to the Recovery

⁹² Ibid.

⁹³ Ibid.

⁹⁴ Ibid.

⁹⁵ See Article 1(6) of Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

⁹⁶ See Article 4 Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

⁹⁷ Ibid.

⁹⁸ See Article 1, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

⁹⁹ Commission, "Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan", COM(2022) 230 final, Brussels 18.05.2022, 17.

¹⁰⁰ European Commission, Press Release "NextGenerationEU: European Commission endorses Germany's recovery and resilience plan", 22 June 2021, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_3133>.

¹⁰¹ European Commission Press Release "NextGenerationEU: European Commission endorses Finland's €2.1 billion recovery and resilience plan", 4 October 2021, available at <https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_21_4992>.

Plans.¹⁰² Therefore, these States preferred accessing unconditional finance on the financial markets, where they can secure low interest rates due to their high credit ratings.¹⁰³ Notwithstanding their preferences, the Regulation establishing the Facility foresees that each Member State has the right to request support in the form of loans until August 2023.¹⁰⁴ REPowerEU aims at channelling these unused resources to Member States that have an appetite in accessing them, such as Italy and other southern and eastern States, due to their high indebtedness and low credit ratings. That is, they are likely to benefit from cheaper lending by the EU compared to market rates.¹⁰⁵ To this purpose, all Member States will be given a limited period from the entering into force of the REPowerEU Regulation, to express their willingness to receive additional loan support. In this way, the Commission will be able to present a plan in view of re-distributing loans that have not been requested and are unlikely to be requested in the future.

The third way of financing REPowerEU is by re-directing other funds to the Facility to address the REPowerEU objectives. Indeed, Member States will be offered the option to transfer a percentage of their national allocation of cohesion funds to the Facility. Specifically, the proposal of the Commission foresees the voluntary transfer of up to 12.5%¹⁰⁶ of the national allocation of cohesion funds governed by the Common Provision Regulation¹⁰⁷ and up to 12.5% of the initial allocation under the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development Regulation to support initiatives included in the REPowerEU chapter.¹⁰⁸ In other words, each Member State may decide to allocate commitment appropriations of these funds to the new targets. The political agreement recently reached between the European Parliament and Council on the final text of REPowerEU Regulation excludes the possibility to transfer funds under the Agricultural Fund for Rural Development Regulation, while allowing Member States to transfer partially or totally funds from the Brexit Adjustment Reserve to the RRF.¹⁰⁹ In addition, the recently reached agreement guarantees that Member States may use unspent Cohesion Policy funds under 2014-2020 allocation to endow direct support to vulnerable families and small and medium-sized enterprises.¹¹⁰ This latest initiative is

¹⁰² Rosalba Famà, cit. note 90.

¹⁰³ Cinzia Alcidi and others, 'Who will really benefit from the Next Generation EU funds?' October 2020, CEPS, 2.

¹⁰⁴ See article 14 of Regulation (EU) 241/2021.

¹⁰⁵ Cinzia Alcidi and others, cit. note 103.

¹⁰⁶ This number is reached adding a 7.5% transfer possibility for REPowerEU objectives building on the already available 5% transfer possibility foreseen in the Regulation establishing the Facility, see Article 7 Regulation (EU) 241/2021.

¹⁰⁷ Regulation (EU) 2021/1060.

¹⁰⁸ Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814, 14.

¹⁰⁹ See Commission, Press Release 'Commission welcomes political agreement on REPowerEU under the Recovery and Resilience Facility', 14 December 2022.

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*

named “Supporting Affordable Energy” (SAFE) and is aimed at protecting the most vulnerable from the increased energy costs.¹¹¹ This third way of financing REPowerEU introduces more flexibility attached to the cohesion funds. It allows the EU to merge resources in a single “basket” and deploy them to address emerging priorities. The following section focuses on the exact functioning of REPowerEU.

4. The REPowerEU governance

The model envisaged in the energy plan follows the same framework established with NGEU, adapting it to emerging energy needs. The Commission believes that the Recovery and Resilience Plans have demonstrated to be highly suitable to implement urgent priorities in a joint EU framework.¹¹² Therefore, Member States willing to receive additional funding under REPowerEU must submit a Recovery and Resilience Plan which includes a REPowerEU chapter. As previously analysed, additional support may be requested in the form of grants financed by the auctioning of ETS allowances, loans still available under the RRF and voluntary transfer of the national allocation of funds under shared management programmes or the Brexit Adjustment Fund. It is up to each Member State to decide the amount and typology of support to request.

As to the content of the REPowerEU chapter, this new section of the Recovery and Resilience Plans must outline new energy-related actions and their corresponding milestones and targets. REPowerEU measures may be either new reforms and investments or the scaling-up of reforms and investments already included in the Recovery Plans of the respective Member State aimed at driving the green transition. The REPowerEU addendum may also replace measures that are no longer achievable due to objective circumstances,¹¹³ following the procedure enshrined in Article 21 of the Regulation establishing the Recovery and Resilience Facility. In general, REPowerEU allows Member States to slightly revise the Recovery Plans and make them fit with the emerging needs.

REPowerEU chapters must include measures that address the REPowerEU objectives analysed in the previous section and must explain how they contribute to security of energy supply of the EU. To that extent, the recently issued Country Specific Recommendations addressing energy-related issues and suggesting to each Member State the way forward. REPowerEU chapters must consider the

¹¹¹ Ibid.

¹¹² Commission, “Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the European Council, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions, REPowerEU Plan”, COM(2022) 230 final, Brussels 18.05.2022, 16.

¹¹³ See Commission Notice Guidance on Recovery and Resilience Plans in the context of REPowerEU 2022/C 214/01, available at <[<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022XC0531\(01\)>](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52022XC0531(01))> .

content of these Country Specific Recommendations.¹¹⁴ Therefore, also the governance of the REPowerEU is embedded in the European Semester.

After the submission of the REPowerEU chapters, the Commission will evaluate them relying on new assessment criteria. In particular, the Commission must verify whether reforms and investments effectively contribute towards diversification of Union's energy supply or reduction of dependence on fossil fuels before 2030.¹¹⁵ Finally, on a proposal from the Commission, the Council approves the REPowerEU chapter by means of an implementing decision.

It is interesting to observe that most of the REPowerEU objectives have a European dimension, however the implementation of many measures remains with the Member States. The interdependence and complementarity of the two levels of governance, national and supranational, is crucial to maximize the impact of the actions for the benefit of all European citizens. This upcoming European energy plan opens the way to a ground-breaking phase of multi-level governance, where targeted projects having European relevance are financed by European resources, while being located and implemented within the territory of a Member State.

5. REPowerEU's legal innovations

This section analyses the legal innovations brought by REPowerEU. The first attains the shift of additional fiscal powers to the EU. The second regards the capacity of the Union to finance its industrial plan in the form of grants classified as external assigned revenue. The third innovation looks at the possibility to redirect Union resources to address unexpected shocks.

First, REPowerEU enables the Union to drive political priorities such as reducing Union dependency on fossil fuels and ensuring diversification of energy supplies. Economists have defined REPowerEU as the “largest industrial policy program ever targeted in the EU.”¹¹⁶ Supranational policies envisaged in the plan are delivered by investing common resources in cross-border actions or projects contributing to ensure EU energy security. The wording “economic policy” refers to a set of structural

¹¹⁴ See for example the Country Specific Recommendations issued for Italy, European Commission, “Recommendation for a Council Recommendation on the 2022 National Reform Programme of Italy and delivering a Council opinion on the 2022 Stability Programme of Italy” Brussels 23 May 2022. In this document, the Commission suggests to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and diversify energy import, overcome bottlenecks to increase the capacity of internal gas transmission, develop electricity interconnections, accelerate the deployment of additional renewable energy capacities and adopt measures to increase energy efficiency and to promote sustainable mobility.

¹¹⁵ Commission, Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814, 15.

¹¹⁶ Massimo Amato and others, cit. note 16.

policies that include industrial and regional ones led by economic considerations.¹¹⁷ As it is well known, this field of policies remains within Member States' prerogatives. Therefore, REPowerEU continues the path towards the transfer of fiscal powers to the EU, including the capacity of the Union to set up a supranational strategic economic policy.¹¹⁸

Second, as discussed before, the REPowerEU plan will be financed by loans, cohesion funds and new grants. The latter are funded by proceeds from the auctioning of ETS and must constitute external assigned revenue¹¹⁹ for the purpose of Article 21 (5) of the Financial Regulation.¹²⁰ As known, the Financial Regulation sets up rules applicable to the implementation of the Union budget. For this reason, it is also called the European “financial bible”.¹²¹ It is worth recalling that also the Regulation establishing a Recovery Instrument classifies funds to be used for non-repayable support as external assigned revenue.¹²² By doing so, NGEU and REPowerEU's grants are placed outside the budget and excluded from the budgetary procedure. This settlement was critically defined by Leino and Ruffert as a legal trick¹²³ to “circumvent” Article 310 TFEU, the principle of budgetary balance. The Commission as well is aware that this way of proceeding deviates from standard practices, however, the Commission justifies it based on the exceptional circumstances caused by the Covid-19.¹²⁴ Such a solution raises democratic challenges and urges constitutional adaptations to ensure transparency, democracy and accountability.¹²⁵

REPowerEU transforms an exceptional measure into the new normal, or, at least, it replicates an exceptional legal settlement introduced with NGEU. It is true that the amount of money disbursed under NGEU in the form of grants is 18 times the amount of REPowerEU and, therefore, is not comparable from a quantitative perspective. However, REPowerEU non-repayable support is meaningful. As anticipated in the introduction, since the creation of NGEU, commentators have wondered if it would be a one-off measure or a blueprint for further interventions.¹²⁶ REPowerEU proves that NGEU is a legal architecture that can be relied upon beyond the pandemic. This is self-

¹¹⁷ Kaarlo Tuori and Klaus Tuori, “The Eurozone crisis. A constitutional analysis”, Cambridge studies in European Law and Policies, 2014, 31.

¹¹⁸ See Federico Fabbrini, cit. note 3, 194 who argued that NGEU transfers fiscal powers to the EU.

¹¹⁹ See Article 1 and 4 of Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council amending Regulation (EU) 2021/241 as regards REPowerEU chapters in recovery and resilience plans and amending Regulation (EU) 2021/1060, Regulation (EU) 2021/2115, Directive 2003/87/EC and Decision (EU) 2015/1814.

¹²⁰ Article 21(5) of Regulation (EU, Euratom) 2018/1046 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

¹²¹ Corinne Delon Desmoulin, ‘Droit budgétaire de l’Union européenne’, LGDJ 2011, 44.

¹²² External assigned revenue (EAR) must be marginal; however, since the introduction of NGEU, the characteristic of marginality is not respected anymore by EAR. See on this point Alexander Mathis, ‘Assigned revenue in the Recovery Plan. The frog that wishes to be as big as the ox?’, Briefing requested by the BUDH Committee, PE 656.549 – July 2020.

¹²³ Päivi Leino-Sandberg and Matthis Ruffert, cit. note 3, 433-472.

¹²⁴ Commission, ‘Q&A: Next Generation EU - Legal Construction’, 9 June 2020.

¹²⁵ Ibid.

¹²⁶ See note 3.

evident by looking at the legal structure of REPowerEU that, as analysed in the previous sections, is fully embedded in NGEU and replicates its functioning. Second, observing the distribution criteria set out in the REPowerEU proposal it is possible to conclude that they favour Member States most affected by the energy crisis. These parameters consider the degree of dependency on imported fossil fuels per region. They show the need for the EU to redistribute resources to tackle asymmetric shocks and an attempt to boost solidarity in times of crisis. Third, the process of adaptation of the Recovery Plan to the emerging energy crisis is legally feasible thanks to the broad cohesion legal basis chosen for the Recovery and Resilience Facility. Indeed, Article 175 (3) TFEU allows the EU to adopt specific actions when such actions are proved necessary outside existing funds. The term “action” is particularly vague and open to interpretation. It encompasses all types of intervention. The only requirement foreseen is the action to pass a “necessity test” and to be innovative compared to existing funds. Both requirements are met considering the additional REPowerEU chapter of reforms and investments linked to the energy crisis. Indeed, as it is well known, currently there are no other funds - outside the RRF - that link the disbursement of funds to the realization of reforms and investments linked to the crisis.

Additional legal innovation brought by REPowerEU attains the use of structural funds. That is, the proposed amendments introduce flexibility to the structure of cohesion funds, which is characterized by rigidity. As well known, the Union budget spending side is constrained by the Multiannual Financial Framework (MFF). The MFF sets in advance the maximum amount of spending in the EU annual budgets for a seven-year period. This pre-allocation impedes the budget to provide short-term crisis responses.¹²⁷ As analysed, REPowerEU allows Member States to transfer up to 12.5% of the national allocation under shared management programmes to the RRF, thus introducing an element of flexibility and adaptability.

In a nutshell, REPowerEU empowers the EU to deliver fiscal policies with a European dimension, such as reducing dependency on fossil fuels. Moreover, it attempts to address the weakness of the European budget as identified in the Monti Report.¹²⁸ That is, on the one hand, the absence of flexibility and influence for short-term crisis intervention, and, on the other hand, the need to adopt a balanced budget. The first weakness is addressed by introducing flexibility to the system of cohesion funds, endowing the budget with an anti-cyclical economic stabilisation function. While the duty to

¹²⁷ Monti Group, ‘Future financing of the EU. Final report and recommendations of the High-Level Group on Own Resources’ December 2016. See also First assessment Report of the High-level Group on Own Resources, Brussels, 17 December 2014.

¹²⁸ *Ibid.*

adopt a balanced budget is respected by recurring to the category of external assigned revenues, although being a sub-optimal solution.

Notwithstanding it was built as a one-off measure and crisis response initiative,¹²⁹ NGEU's potential goes beyond the Covid-19 crisis.¹³⁰ The Facility is therefore a tool capable to pool resources to be assigned to urgent investments. As observed, funds disbursed to the Member States in the form of grants and loans remain external to the standard budget, thus determining an accountability gap. REPowerEU is the first step towards transforming NGEU into a permanent feature of the EU. However, it is not accompanied by a reform in the field of Union budget aimed at improving accountability. Therefore, the advent of REPowerEU urges further constitutional adaptations by the EU.

6. Conclusion

The energy crisis seriously threatens the European Union's successful recovery from Covid-19. Next Generation EU (NGEU) was adopted to avoid an economic recession due to the lockdowns. The Russian military aggression of Ukraine has triggered serious concerns about the EU energy security. Indeed, the EU was ill-equipped for the energy consequences of a land war on the European continent, which destroys a historical and vital relationship between the west and the east of the European continent. The EU must ensure energy security for its citizens. To do so, the EU seeks to diversify its energy supplies and accelerate the adoption of renewables. Both measures require huge public investments.

The creative construction of Next Generation EU allowed the EU, for the first time since its inception, to combine reforms and investments financed by an enlarged EU budget. More importantly, the NGEU has generated a framework that may remain within the EU toolbox to tackle future emergencies. The follow-up creation of REPowerEU proves this assessment. The upcoming energy plan is fully embedded within the legal architecture of NGEU while enhancing its objectives. The introduction of energy-related objectives shows that the NGEU is flexible and capable of delivering new results, which go well beyond the pandemic. Thanks to the adoption of REPowerEU and the

¹²⁹ See Article 5 of Council Decision (EU, Euratom) 2020/2053 on the system of own resources of the European Union and repealing Decision 2014/335/EU Euratom. See also recital 6 of Council Regulation (EU) 2020/2094 of 14 December 2020 establishing a European Recovery Instrument to support the recovery in the aftermath of the Covid-19 crisis. This recital also provides that the support provided should be used only for addressing the adverse economic consequences of the pandemic or the immediate funding to prevent the resurfacing of Covid-19 crisis. However, as it is well-known recitals have not the same legal value as the articles.

¹³⁰ The German Constitutional Court has recently issued its ruling stating that NGEU funds can be used exclusively to address the Covid-19 crisis and that this initiative is time-limited <https://www.bundesverfassungsgericht.de/SharedDocs/Pressemitteilungen/EN/2022/bvg22-103.html>.

mobilization of European resources the EU might propel the green transition and be able to finance the implementation of its European Green Deal.

Moreover, this paper concludes with three preliminary findings. First, the adoption of REPowerEU continues the path toward the transfer of fiscal powers to the EU, as the EU is now able to define its energy strategy and finance related investments, powered by a reformed RRF. Second, REPowerEU resources to be distributed in the form of non-repayable support to the Member States will be classified as external assigned revenue and, therefore, placed outside the European budget. Third, REPowerEU introduces more flexibility in the use of cohesion funds, thus breaking with past rigidity which impeded to address unforeseen circumstances with pre-allocated funds.

Likely, the current crisis linked to the unlawful invasion of Ukraine will not be the last one the EU has to face. Therefore, the actual energy crisis and climate change challenges offer an opportunity to reflect upon the need of introducing an NGEU-a-like mechanism as a lasting feature of the EU constitutional architecture to pool resources for strategic policies and investments. History will tell.

Annex 1

Figure 1 Gas pipeline map. Map showing the Brotherhood and TAG pipelines authored by Marco Siddi in “Economic cooperation between Italy and the Russian Federation: History, success stories and challenges”, 27 December 2019.